

OrganKits project

OrganKits partners have developed several activities and have several updates to share! The main activities of our project are presented in this 5th newsletter.

Want to find more?

Contact us or visit our website.

Top stories

OrganKits in Action: Highlights from Kuşadası Bahçeşehir College

In this cycle, our students dove into the fascinating world of body systems with creativity, curiosity, and hands-on exploration!

[Read more...](#)

Platon Schools Complete Second Cycle of OrganKits Activities

The second cycle of the Erasmus+ OrganKits project was successfully completed at Platon Schools in Greece, with students diving deeper into science through hands-on learning and real anatomical models.

[Read more...](#)

Plastination Activities in OrganKits: A Major Milestone Achieved

Over the past months, Discover-IN (Murcia) has successfully plastinated a total of 448 real organ specimens, including hearts, lungs, brains, stomachs, kidneys, and more—sourced from ovine, bovine, and swine origins.

[Read more...](#)

OrganKits lands in the Museo de la Ciencia y el Agua de la Región de Murcia

We are thrilled to announce our collaboration with the Murcia City Council to host two major events of the OrganKits project...

[See more](#)

